

Appendix 1. Full-length student survey

THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC HAS CHANGED OUR BEHAVIOUR PATTERNS, BOTH SOCIAL AND ACADEMIC.

SECTION 1. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

1. COMPARED TO 2019 (BEFORE THE PANDEMIC), WHAT CHANGES DO YOU PERCEIVE IN YOUR BEHAVIOUR OR THE BEHAVIOUR OF YOUR FAMILY AND FRIENDS ON A SOCIAL LEVEL? DO YOU SEE ANY PREVENTION MEASURES STILL WORKING? PLEASE, TICK THE ONES YOU PERCEIVE FROM THE LIST BELOW:
2. IF YOU TICK “USE OF MASK” IN QUESTION 1, PLEASE INDICATE IN WHICH CONTEXT.
3. IF YOU TICK “OTHERS” IN QUESTION 1, PLEASE INDICATE WHICH.
4. HOW DO THOSE BEHAVIOURAL CHANGES AND PREVENTION MEASURES AFFECT CURRENT SOCIAL COMMUNICATION FROM YOUR POINT OF VIEW?
5. AND, WITHIN THE UNIVERSITY CONTEXT? WHAT BEHAVIOURAL CHANGES AND PREVENTION MEASURES HAVE THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC INTRODUCED AND HAVE REMAINED IN THE STUDENTS’ AND SCHOLARS’ BEHAVIOURS WITHIN THE UNIVERSITY? TICK THE ONES YOU PERCEIVE FROM THE LIST BELOW:
6. IF YOU TICK “MORE PREVENTIVE DISTANCE IN UNIVERSITY SETTINGS” IN THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, PLEASE INDICATE WHERE (PLEASE SPECIFY THE SETTINGS).
7. IF YOU TICK “USE OF MASK” IN THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, PLEASE INDICATE IN WHICH CONTEXTS.
8. IF YOU TICK “MORE USE OF DIGITAL RESOURCES”, PLEASE INDICATE WHICH TYPE.
9. IF YOU TICK “MORE USE OF COMPUTER APPLICATIONS”, PLEASE INDICATE WHAT TYPE.
10. IF YOU TICK “OTHERS”, PLEASE INDICATE WHICH.
11. HOW DO THOSE BEHAVIOURAL CHANGES AND PREVENTION MEASURES AFFECT CURRENT ACADEMIC COMMUNICATION AND STUDENTS’ INTERACTION WITHIN UNIVERSITY PREMISES FROM YOUR POINT OF VIEW?
12. DO YOU THINK THE PANDEMIC HAS PRODUCED CHANGES THAT REMAIN AND CONTINUE TO DEVELOP IN CURRENT TEACHING AND LEARNING/STUDYING METHODOLOGIES?
13. IF YOU TICK “YES” IN QUESTION 12, PLEASE INDICATE THE CHANGES YOU PERCEIVE IN THE CURRENT TEACHING INTERACTION AND METHODOLOGIES.
14. IF YOU TICK “YES” IN QUESTION 10, PLEASE INDICATE THE CHANGES YOU PERCEIVE IN YOUR CURRENT LEARNING AND STUDY METHODOLOGIES.
15. AT THIS TIME, WHAT DO YOU THINK IS THE TYPE OF MESSAGE THAT BEST REACHES THE POPULATION REGARDING HEALTH ALERTS AND PREVENTION MEASURES? WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING INFORMATION CHANNELS DO YOU CONSIDER MOST USEFUL FOR YOU AND YOUR FAMILY MEMBERS ON A SOCIAL LEVEL?
16. IF YOU TICK “OTHERS” IN THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, PLEASE SAY WHICH.

17. FROM THE TYPES OF MESSAGES ABOVE (FREQUENT IN SOCIAL COMMUNICATION), WHICH DO YOU CONSIDER THE MOST AND LEAST USEFUL TO TRANSMIT ESSENTIAL INFORMATION?
18. OF THE TYPES OF MESSAGES MENTIONED ABOVE, WHICH DO YOU CONSIDER MOST INTERESTING AND USEFUL FOR STUDENTS IN ACADEMIC AND UNIVERSITY ENVIRONMENTS?
19. IF YOU TICK “OTHERS” IN THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, PLEASE SAY WHICH.
20. FROM THE TYPES OF MESSAGES ABOVE (FREQUENT IN UNIVERSITY COMMUNICATION), WHICH DO YOU CONSIDER THE MOST AND LEAST EFFECTIVE TO TRANSMIT ESSENTIAL INFORMATION?
21. AT THIS TIME, IN WHAT UNIVERSITY CONTEXTS (INCLUDING THE CAMPUS SURROUNDINGS) CAN YOU OBSERVE WARNING MESSAGES AND CHANGES IN REGULATIONS AND NORMS RELATED TO THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC? PLEASE TICK THE ONES YOU PERCEIVE FROM THE LIST BELOW:
22. IF YOU TICK “OTHERS” IN THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, PLEASE SAY WHICH.

SECTION 2. PANCOM’S LEXICAL-SEMANTIC DIMENSION

23. THE NOTIONS OF “SEMANTIC FRAME” AND “LEXICAL FIELD” ARE ESSENTIAL FOR ANALYSING MULTIMODAL AND HYBRID MESSAGES. WHAT COMES TO YOUR MIND WHEN YOU HEAR THESE CONCEPTS? HOW WOULD YOU DEFINE/EXPLAIN THEM?
24. IN WHAT SUBJECTS OF YOUR UNIVERSITY DEGREE HAVE YOU LEARNT ABOUT THESE CONCEPTS, OR DO YOU CONSIDER YOU SHOULD HAVE LEARNT ABOUT THEM?
25. DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC, MANY DIGITAL POSTERS INCLUDED KEYWORDS TO CONVEY SOCIAL COHESION AND COMMUNITY, HEALTH, AND PROTECTION TO POLITELY ASK CITIZENS TO WEAR FACE MASKS, KEEP SOCIAL DISTANCE, ETC. IN YOUR OPINION, WERE THESE MESSAGES CLEAR? OR HAVE YOU EVER INTERPRETED THESE MESSAGES AS CONTRADICTORY? IF YES, PLEASE INDICATE IF THE POSSIBLE AMBIGUITY COULD LIE IN THE TEXT, IN THE IMAGE, OR MAY BE CAUSED BY BOTH.
26. WHAT DO YOU KNOW ABOUT “RHETORICAL FIGURES OR STRATEGIES” (APPLIED TO SOCIAL CONTEXTS/MESSAGES)? PLEASE BRIEFLY EXPLAIN WHAT YOU THINK THEY ARE AND WHY THEY ARE USED.
27. IN WHAT SUBJECTS OF YOUR UNIVERSITY DEGREE HAVE YOU LEARNT ABOUT RHETORICAL FIGURES APPLIED TO SOCIAL COMMUNICATION, OR DO YOU CONSIDER YOU SHOULD HAVE LEARNT ABOUT THEM?
28. DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC, MANY DIGITAL POSTERS (E.G. MEMES) INCLUDED HUMOROUS STRATEGIES RELATED TO THE PANDEMIC. WHAT IS YOUR OPINION ON USING HUMOUR AND PARODY IN THESE TEXTS? DO YOU CONSIDER THEM EFFECTIVE IN TIMES OF PANDEMICS?
29. THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC HAS GENERATED NEW ANGLICISMS (E.G. SOCIAL DISTANCING, HOMESCHOOLING, HOME OFFICE), NEOLOGISMS (E.G. HERD IMMUNITY), NEW SAFETY/ADMINISTRATIVE TERMS (E.G. SOCIAL DISTANCE, DISTANCE RULES, HYGIENE RULES, ETC.), OR EVEN COMMON WORDS WHICH HAVE ACQUIRED A NEW MEANING (E.G. RISK AREA). DO

YOU STILL USE THESE WORDS AND/OR HEAR THEM USED AROUND YOU? COULD YOU PLEASE ARGUE YOUR ANSWER WITH EXAMPLES?

SECTION 3. PANCOM'S FUNCTIONAL DIMENSION

30. HOW MUCH DO YOU KNOW ABOUT THE NOTION OF "LANGUAGE REGISTER" AND "REGISTER VARIATION"?

31. IN WHAT SUBJECTS OF YOUR UNIVERSITY DEGREE HAVE YOU LEARNED ABOUT REGISTER VARIATION, OR DO YOU CONSIDER YOU SHOULD HAVE LEARNT ABOUT IT?

32. IN THE FOLLOWING DIGITAL POSTER FROM FACEBOOK, DO YOU THINK THAT THE REGISTER USED IS ...?

33. REGARDING THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, PLEASE BRIEFLY EXPLAIN THE REASON FOR YOUR CHOICE

34. ARE YOU FAMILIAR WITH THE NOTIONS OF "SPEECH ACT" AND "LINGUISTIC POLITENESS"? PLEASE DEFINE THESE CONCEPTS FROM YOUR POINT OF VIEW.

35. IN WHAT SUBJECTS OF YOUR UNIVERSITY DEGREE HAVE YOU LEARNT ABOUT SPEECH ACTS AND LINGUISTIC POLITENESS, OR DO YOU CONSIDER YOU SHOULD HAVE LEARNT ABOUT THEM?

36. WHEN READING AND INTERPRETING DIGITAL POSTERS ON PREVENTIVE HEALTH MESSAGES, DO YOU THINK YOU ARE BEING INFORMED, ADVISED, RECOMMENDED, WARNED, INSTRUCTED, OR A MIXTURE OF THE ABOVE?

37. HOW MUCH DO YOU KNOW ABOUT "METADISOURSE STRATEGIES"? HAVE YOU HEARD ABOUT "INTERACTIVE" AND "INTERACTIONAL" METADISOURSE STRATEGIES? COULD YOU EXPLAIN THEIR MAIN FUNCTION OR MENTION WHAT YOU KNOW ABOUT THEM?

38. IN WHAT SUBJECTS OF YOUR UNIVERSITY DEGREE HAVE YOU LEARNT ABOUT METADISOURSE IN CURRENT COMMUNICATION, OR DO YOU CONSIDER YOU SHOULD HAVE LEARNT ABOUT IT?

39. WHICH OF THESE TWO DIGITAL POSTERS DO YOU CONSIDER MOST CONVENIENT TO CONVINCING THE VIEWER ABOUT THE MESSAGE THEY CONVEY?

40. WHAT ASPECTS DO YOU CONSIDER THE MOST EFFECTIVE IN THE PREVIOUS MESSAGES? CAN YOU RELATE THESE PICTURES WITH SOME INTERACTIONAL METADISOURSE STRATEGIES TO IMPACT THE VIEWER?

41. HAVE YOU EVER HEARD THE NOTIONS OF "POSITIVE" AND "NEGATIVE" LINGUISTIC POLITENESS?

42. WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING DIGITAL POSTERS DO YOU FEEL MORE INVOLVED AND WILLING TO DO THE ACTION ACCORDING TO THE MESSAGE? MORE THAN ONE OPTION MAY BE CHOSEN.

43. CONCERNING THE PREVIOUS QUESTION, PLEASE BRIEFLY EXPLAIN THE REASON FOR YOUR CHOICE REGARDING POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE POLITENESS. WHICH ONES DO YOU SEE AS MORE CONSIDERATE?

44. WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING DIGITAL POSTERS DO YOU THINK IS MORE IMPOSING AND WHY? WHICH ELEMENT OF THE IMAGE CATCHES YOUR ATTENTION THE MOST AND WHY?

45. PLEASE BRIEFLY EXPLAIN THE REASONS FOR YOUR CHOICE IN QUESTION 44.

46. WHAT TEXTUAL AND/OR VISUAL ELEMENTS OF THE FOLLOWING DIGITAL POSTERS MIGHT MAKE THE VIEWER OF THESE IMAGES FEEL PRONE TO COLLABORATE OR FEEL SOMEHOW PATRONISED/INTIMIDATED?

SECTION 4. PANCOM'S MULTI-SEMIOTIC DIMENSION

47. IN RELATION TO THE THEORY OF VISUAL GRAMMAR, THERE ARE ESSENTIAL MULTIMODAL AND PARALINGUISTIC FACTORS THAT SIGNIFICANTLY AFFECT THE MEANING OF PANDEMIC MESSAGES. PLEASE INDICATE, FROM YOUR POINT OF VIEW, WHICH ELEMENTS BELOW ARE MORE HELPFUL WHEN UNDERSTANDING THE GLOBAL MESSAGE. MORE THAN ONE OPTION MAY BE CHOSEN.

48. IF YOU TICK "OTHERS", PLEASE SPECIFY WHICH ONES.

49. WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING IMAGES INCORPORATED INTO THE FOLLOWING EXAMPLES OF DIGITAL POSTERS RELATED TO THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC DO YOU THINK IS MORE IMPOSING AND WHY? WHICH ELEMENT OF THE IMAGE CATCHES YOUR ATTENTION THE MOST AND WHY?

50. IN WHAT SUBJECTS OF YOUR UNIVERSITY DEGREE HAVE YOU LEARNT ABOUT THESE ELEMENTS AND VISUAL GRAMMAR, OR DO YOU CONSIDER YOU SHOULD HAVE LEARNT ABOUT THEM?